

LiCeWO₄)₂ Polymorphs: A Novel Anode Material for Lithium-Ion Batteries Crystal Structure Correlation via Neutron Diffraction Study

K M Archana¹, Debasmita Dwivedi², James Hester³, Diptikanta Swain⁴,
Prabeer Barpanda^{2†} and Nalini G Sundaram^{1*}

^{1,1*}Poornaprajna Institute of Scientific Research, Devanahalli-562 164, Bangalore, India
(Recognized by the DSIR, Govt. of India and Manipal University)

^{2,2†}Faraday Materials Laboratory, Materials Research Center, Indian Institute of Science, C.V. Raman Avenue,
Bangalore 560012, India

³Australian Nuclear Science Technology and Organization, OPAL, Lucas Heights, Sydney, Australia, NSW 2234

⁴Solid State Structural Chemistry Unit, IISc, Bengaluru, India

E-mail: nalini@poornaprajna.org and Mobile No: 9741158859

Abstract

Rare earth oxide materials are multifunctional disordered materials widely studied for laser media optoelectronics¹⁻³. Among various rare earth oxides, LiRE(WO₄)₂ (RE=lanthanides) exist in a wide variety of crystal systems and also exhibits polymorphism^{4, 5}. More recently these materials are also been used in lithium ion battery applications and shown interesting electrochemical behavior^{6, 7}.

In the present study, polymorphs of LiCe(WO₄)₂ were synthesized via solgel method and Rietveld refinements were carried out using high temperature Neutron diffraction data collected at ANSTO. Further, LiCe(WO₄)₂ polymorphs were examined using galvanostatic measurements as anode materials for lithium ion batteries for the first time. To the best of our knowledge this is the first study elucidating synthesis, detailed crystal structure analysis, structural phase transitions and the electrochemical properties of LiCe(WO₄)₂ polymorphs. Hence, the insights of our study would be helpful for scientific community to achieve better results from these materials with modifications or surface coating in future studies.

Key words: Polymorphs, Phase transitions, Neutron diffraction and Anode battery material.

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